

Evaluation of NAAC Accredited “A” Grade College Library Websites of Goa State

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Abstract

At present large number of users depends upon web content of the concerned college libraries. The researcher here attempted to analyze websites of NAAC accredited “A” grade college libraries in the state of Goa. The analysis includes basic information available in the library website of the concerned colleges such as total number of webpage’s, web links, general information about the college library, facilities available in the library, its rules and regulations, its print and electronic resources, services, sections in the library etc. These parameters have been measured and compared together and concluded with the major findings and recommended few suggestions.

Keywords: Website, Analysis, E-Resources, NAAC Accredited Institutions, Library Websites, Goa

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1. Introduction:

Goa enjoys a place of pride in the country as one of the most literate states of India. It was liberated from Portuguese rule in 1961 and has registered impressive progress in the field of education since then. The State has achieved 87.40 percent literacy as per 2011 population census.

Goa University is the only University in the State of Goa, which was established in June 1985 by an Act of Goa Government, is located on a picturesque campus spread over 427.49 acres area of Taleigao plateau within close vicinity of the capital city of Panaji in North Goa. Today Goa University is a university of affiliated colleges, 54 of which are distributed across Goa, 26 in general education and 28 in professional educations, with a total enrolment of about 26,000. Colleges of General Education (govt-5, non-govt-21) are 26 in number and these colleges are providing higher education to students under Arts, Commerce and Science streams. All these colleges are affiliated to the Goa University that controls all the academic aspects of these colleges.

Information technology (IT) is radically changing the face of academic libraries, their organizational structure and the manner in which they deliver services to their stakeholders. Academic libraries are being asked to provide quality service with fewer resources to users. A website is a key tool for information and for academic purpose, it considered as a prime importance for pioneer information and awareness. The College libraries are the center and heart of the any academic institutions. Academic libraries bear the challenge of meeting information needs of patrons varying from fresh students' to eminent scholars.

According to Battleson, Booth and Weintrop (2001), "library websites are evolving into information gateways, unlocking access to library resources and services as well as electronic indexes and databases, primary research materials, and the internet at large". A library website (academic or public) facilitates its users to connect with the library 24 hours a day. "Today it is possible for student to conduct research for papers without ever stepping in the academic library. They can ask reference questions virtually; conduct research in databases; and place interlibrary loan requests electronically. All of these functions utilize library websites, requiring those websites to be timely and easy to use" (Connell, 2008, p.121). Any library website provides the bridge between library users and resources. Users can access their desired information from website from anywhere in the world.

The academic library websites are mirror of their collection, services and they play a key role in the learning and research processes. The users are more accessible from the library websites than to the physical library itself. In this way, "academic library websites will become user-focused gateways to rich, quality content and, in doing so, re-establish the campus library's central role in the learning and research process" (Detlor and Lewis, 2006)

2. Literature Review

There are many interesting studies on content analysis of different academic library websites; previous analyses of web sites have examined the variety of factors. The following review of the literature demonstrates how web sites have been scrutinized as well as the categories and elements found that are most relevant to evaluation.

Mohd. Haneefa K and Anjana Venugopal M.K analysed the contents of national library websites in Asia and found that websites of national libraries of Asian countries have a common pattern of website content and design. Found that only few national library websites served their users with web 2.0 technologies. Michalec, Mychaelyn evaluated contents like design, colours, background color, font style, links and navigation bars special effects of Art library websites. And found that, color schemes for art library home pages are fairly simple and the number of colors is limited. There is no difference in color use between academic / art school libraries and museum libraries.

Jayshankar R and Ramesh Babu B examined the websites of forty-five universities in Tamilnadu comprising of twenty seven state and eighteen private universities and identified the domain systems of the websites, analyses the number of webpages and linkpages and at the end calculated Web Impact Factor. A survey conducted by Vasantha Raju N and Harinarayana N.S of thirty library websites of top science universities around the world for their design features with special reference to usability. And found that, only 30% of the websites contain video contents and none of the websites contained exclusive audio files. Attempt of Anna Kaushik in evaluating and analyzing the services, facilities and other information available on the library websites of 28 National Institute of Technology (NITs) in the month of February, 2015, by using a checklist. The results of this study revealed that the majority of NIT library websites are providing information with regard to their name, logo, about library book collection, electronic resources, accuracy, diverse services and sections, but, lacking of library mission statements, currency, and reliability search interfaces, Web 2.0 applications and cutting edge technologies like cloud-based services. This study helped to judge the quality and diverse facilities present on the 28 NIT library websites in India. Analysis of engineering college library websites in Tumkur district of Karnataka state, conducted by Kannappanavar, B. U.; Jayaprakash, and Bachalapur, M M, found that Engineering College libraries are not maintaining a separate library website, and limited information is provided through their institution website. These libraries are providing automated services to its users and sufficient information is not furnished in their college library websites.

Jaydeep Mehta and Mayank Trivedi in their article "Contents of University Library websites of Central Universities of India: An analysis" discussed the significant approach of library information available on the university website. They covered 45 Central University Libraries website of India. Analysis found that details available on the websites express various aspects of library information. Sarwesh Pareek and Dinesh K. Gupta *Vardhaman Mahaveer in their article "Academic Library Websites in Rajasthan"* conducted a survey of 52 academic library websites, i.e. government, deemed self-financed universities and research centers in Rajasthan based on 133-item checklist. And analysed their content and navigational strengths and weaknesses and recommended for developing better library web sites. Whereas, Akhandanand Shukla and Adhitya Tripathi examined the status of library website content and compared 20 central universities and 19 institute of national importance (i.e.:- IIT, IIM and others) and

suggested that the library website of institute of national importance have better content awareness than central university library website as per the identified criteria.

3. Objectives of the Study

3.1 To know the similarity and differences among the NAAC accredited “A” grade college libraries in Goa State.

3.2 To examine the basic facilities and services provided by these libraries and rank them based on their respective features.

3.3 To suggest measures for the improvement of these library websites.

3.4 To calculate the simple Web Impact Factor (WIF) and rank them as per WIF.

4. Scope of the Study

Scope of the study is limited to the NAAC accredited “A” grade college libraries in Goa State. The following are the list of academic libraries selected for the study:

Sl No.	Name of the Colleges	Year of Establishment	Website	NAAC CGPA Score
1.	DCT's Dhempe College of Arts and Science, Panaji	1962	www.dhempecollege.edu.in	3.20
2.	Parvatibai chowgule college of Arts and Science, Margao	1962	www.chowgules.ac.in	3.41
3.	St. Xavier College, Mapusa	1963	www.xaviercollege-go.com	3.36
4.	Carmel College for Women, Nuvem	1964	www.carmelcollegegoa.org	3.02
5.	V.M. Salgaonkar College of Law, Panaji	1973	www.vmslaw.edu	3.29
6.	Dnyanaprassarak Mandal's College and Research Center, Assagao.	1974	www.dmscollege.ac.in	3.02
7.	Government College of Arts, Science and Commerce, Quepem	1989	www.gcq.ac.in	3.23
8.	Rosary College of Commerce and Arts, Navelim	1990	www.rosarycollege.org	3.21

Table 6.3 shows the rules and regulations, timings, membership and staff directory of the concerned college libraries. 62.5% of the college library websites shows the library timings followed by 50% college library websites shown the library rules, 37.5% about library membership and 12.5% colleges included information about the library staff directory.

Table No. 6.4
Library Collection

Types of Collection	CC	DMCRC	DC	GC, Q	PCC	RC	VMSLC	St.XC	Total
Books	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	6(75)
New Arrivals	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	N	1(12.5)
Journal & Magazine	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	6(75)
Newspapers	N	Y	N	Y	Y	N	N	Y	4(50)
CD/DVD's	N	Y	N	N	N	Y	N	N	2(25)
Project Reports	N	Y	N	N	Y	N	N	N	2(25)
Bounded Journals	N	Y	N	N	Y	N	Y	Y	4(50)
Question Papers	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	0

Table 6.4 described the information about the library collection. 75% of the library websites shown about books, journals and magazines, followed by newspapers and bounded journals with 50%. Least information is provided about CD/DVD's and project reports i.e.:- 25%. None of the college library websites displayed information about question papers, which is very important for degree college the students.

Table No. 6.5
Electronic Resources and Facilities

Resources	CC	DMCRC	DC	GC, Q	PCC	RC	VMSLC	St.XC	Total
e-magazines & e-journals	N	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	5(62.5)
e-Books	N	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	5(62.5)
Audio-Video Lectures	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	1(12.5)
Courseware	N	Y	N	N	Y	Y	N	N	3(37.5)
Open Access Resources	N	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	N	4(50)
e-thesis & Dissertations	N	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	N	N	4(50)
Link to other Web Portals	N	Y	N	N	Y	Y	N	N	3 (37.5)
Institutional Repository	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	1(12.5)
Subscription to N-LIST	N	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	N	N	4(50)

Faculty Publications	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	1(12.5)
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Table 6.5 indicates the electronic resources and facilities available in their respective college library websites under the study. 62.5% websites informed about the availability of e-magazines, e-journals and e-books, 50% libraries displayed information about open access resources, e-thesis and dissertations, subscription to N-LIST. Courseware and Link to other web portals is provided by 37.5% college library websites. Information regarding Audio-Video Lectures, Institutional Repository and Faculty Publications are least (i.e.:- 12.5%) provided by the library websites.

Table No. 6. 6
Sections in the Library

Sections	CC	DMCRC	DC	GC, Q	PCC	RC	VMSLC	St.XC	Total
Reference	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	6(75)
Circulation	N	Y	N	N	Y	N	Y	Y	4(50)
Internet Browsing	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	6(75)
Stack	N	Y	N	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	5(62.5)
Reprography	N	Y	N	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	5(62.5)
Discussion Room	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	1(12.5)
Periodical Section	N	Y	N	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	5(62.5)

Table 6.6 shows the different sections available in the respective college libraries. 75% of the college libraries mentioned in their website that, they are having reference section and internet browsing section followed by stack section, reprographic section and periodical section with 62.5%, and circulation section with 50%. Least information (i.e.:-12.5%) is available on the library website about discussion room.

Table No. 6.7
Library Services

Services	CC	DMCRC	DC	GC, Q	PCC	RC	VMSLC	St.XC	Total
Internet Access	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	6(75)
Photocopy	N	Y	N	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	5(62.5)
Reference	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	6(75)
Reading Room	N	Y	N	N	Y	N	Y	Y	4(50)
Discussion Room	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	1(12.5)
Bibliography Compilation	N	Y	N	Y	Y	N	N	N	3 (37.5)
OPAC	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	N	Y	5(62.5)
Book Bank	N	Y	N	N	Y	N	N	N	2(25)

Interlibrary Loan	N	Y	N	Y	N	N	N	N	2(25)
User Orientation	N	N	N	Y	Y	N	N	N	2(25)
User Education Programme	N	N	N	Y	Y	N	N	N	2(25)
CAS	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	0
SDI	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	0
Printing	N	Y	N	Y	Y	N	N	N	3 (37.5)
Scanning	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	1(12.5)

Table 6.7 depicts various services provided by the library. Internet access and reference service information is provided by 75% college library websites, 62.5% libraries mentioned about reprographic service and Online Public Access Catalogues (OPAC). Reading room service, bibliographic compilation service and printing service with 50% and 37.5% respectively. 25% of the library websites mentioned about book bank facility, Inter-library loan, user orientation and user education programme available in their libraries. Least information is provided with the services of discussion room and scanning service with 12.5%.

Table No. 6.8
Value Added Information Services

VAIS	CC	DMCRC	DC	GC, Q	PCC	RC	VMSLC	St.XC	Total
Photo Gallery	N	Y	N	N	N	N	Y	N	2(40)
Library Events & Updates	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	0
Web 2.0 Technologies	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	0
Useful Downloads	N	N	N	Y	Y	N	N	N	2(40)
Job Opportunities and Preparation for Competitive Examinations	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	1(20)

Table 6.8 explains about the Value Added Information Services provided by the college library websites. 40% of the library websites provides information about availability of photo gallery and useful downloads on their websites, and 12.5% of the library website provides information about job

opportunities and preparation for competitive examinations. None of the college library websites provided information about library events and updates, web 2.0 technologies.

Table No. 6.9
Web Impact Factor

Factors	Carmel College	Dnyanprassarak Mandal's College	Dhempe College	Govt. College Quepem	Parvatibai Chowgule College	Rosary College	Salgaonkar Law College	Xavier College	Total
No. of Web Pages	1	19	1	1	30	2	7	8	69 ()
No. of Links Pages	0	55	0	0	71	7	0	0	133 ()

Table 6.9 describes web impact factor of these college library websites. Parvatibai Chougule College library website provides highest thirty number of webpages and seventy-one number of links to its webpage's, followed by Dnyanprassarak Mandal's College with nineteen web pages and fifty-five web links in its website. Rest of the college library website pages and links are very less and it has to be increased for better services to its users.

Table No. 6.10
Ranking of College library websites

Name of the Colleges	General Information	Rules and Membership	Library Collection	Electronic Resources and Facilities	Sections in the Library	Library Services	Value Added Information Services	Total No. of Information	Websites Ranking
Dnyanprassarak Mandal's College	10	04	06	09	07	11	02	49	1
Parvatibai Chougule College	06	03	06	07	06	10	01	39	2
Govt. College Quepem	02	00	03	04	05	09	01	24	3
Salgaonkar Law College	05	02	03	03	06	04	01	24	3
Xavier College	03	03	04	01	06	05	00	22	4
Rosary College	06	00	01	07	00	00	00	14	5
Dhempe College	03	00	02	00	01	01	00	07	6
Carmel College	01	01	00	00	01	02	00	05	7

Table 6.10 indicates ranking of college library websites. Dnyanprassarak Mandal's College and Research Center library website provides highest information about its library collection, facility and services and stood 1st rank. Followed by Parvatibai Chougule College, Government College, Quepem, and VM Salgaonkar Law College. Least information is provided by Carmel College, Dhempe College and Rosary College. All most all the colleges provided general information and library services about their college libraries. Only few college library websites mentioned about the value added services provided by them. Same information is displayed below with the help of bar chart.

7. Findings

7.1 All the college library websites under the study does not have a question paper collection which is very important for graduate and undergraduate students.

7.2 Very less number of college library websites informed about the availability of Audio-Video Lectures, institutional repositories and faculty publications.

7.3 Value added information services like Library events and updates, web 2.0 technologies, job opportunities is not provided by the college library websites.

7.4 Highest number of college library websites (i.e.:- 62.5%) are having only one or two pages of information on their library website.

7.5 Static web pages found on the library website. And absence of web counters on their website to know that how many visitors visited to their college library website.

7.6 None of the college library websites provided information about library events and updates, web 2.0 technologies

8. Suggestions

- 8.1 Some of the college is having their question paper collection in their library software but they have not mentioned about it in their respective library websites.
- 8.2 It is suggested to improve their college library website by providing all the basic required information. Then only library users will make use of the library website more and more.
- 8.3 Now a days lot of Open Access Resources are available on the internet, at least librarians should connect these websites to their college library websites.
- 8.4 Few colleges are provided information in one static web pages only that too very little information. So, it is suggested that the library website should have minimum 8 to 10 webpage information and dynamic website.

9. Conclusion

NAAC accreditations is intended to ensure high quality standards in colleges, even though all the colleges are having NAAC accreditation with 'A' grade, but there are so many differences in the college library websites.

Library and information center main objective is to disseminate information to its users, in a systematic way by saving the users' time (according to fourth law of library science). But college should provide more web pages (space) to the library and librarian should include all the relevant information related to their users in their college library websites.

The academic libraries in India, in particularly college libraries, are improving their service base especially with application of Information technology for access and delivery of e-content to their users. In this process they are also adapting to the change, altering their image, by executing new functions and providing varieties of services in an evolving continuum.

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